
MC-2D: An Efficient and Scalable Multicoupon Scheme

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Electronic multicoupons are the digital version of paper-based booklet of coupons, that allow a customer to obtain goods or services from a merchant typically with discounts or gifts. In this paper, we propose a multicoupon scheme for multi-merchant environments that enhances the security and the efficiency as regards the previous solution that deals with this kind of scenario. On one hand, our scheme meets basic security requirements (unforgeability, reuse detection), but also unsplittability. This fact will help to increase the trust in the part of merchants. On the other hand, we focus on achieving a high degree of privacy for customers (anonymity, unlinkability, confidentiality) that will contribute to gain the trust of the involved customers. Moreover, we provide measures to protect honest parties from dishonest participants, keeping in mind the scalability and efficiency of the multicoupon scheme, to attract customers and merchants. In addition, we show by analytic evaluation that our proposal outperforms the previous solution.

Keywords: electronic multicoupon, multi-merchant, e-commerce, anonymity revocation, security analysis, unforgeability, unsplittability

Received 00 January 2009; revised 00 Month 2009

1. INTRODUCTION

A paper-based coupon is a document that allows a customer to obtain goods or services from a merchant, typically achieving discounts or gifts. Coupons are working properly in conventional commerce, because customers obtain benefits of using them, and so do merchants, increasing sales. We can find some successful examples: booklet for restaurants [1, 2], hotels [3], etc. So, it seems interesting to provide an electronic version of paper-based coupons. The true reality is that electronic coupons topic is receiving a remarkable attention in recent years [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12], but we have not found real experiences (unlike the case of electronic tickets). We can surmise two reasons for this situation. On one hand, we can mention lack of trust for merchants and customers, and lack of privacy for customers. Thus, we need schemes accomplishing some security requirements in order to provide trust and privacy. On the other hand, we need viable and efficient solutions that can be deployed on mobile devices (smart-phones, tablets, PDAs, etc.).

There are paper-based coupons with different features: single coupons or booklet of coupons, anonymous or identified, for one merchant or multiple merchants, transferable or not, etc. Here we

want to provide a scheme with the following initial conditions: multicoupon, multi-merchant, with a high degree of anonymity for customers and not detachable (unsplittable). In this context, and due to our solution is multi-merchant, we must provide more flexibility in this kind of scenario, so it is interesting to allow that a merchant can affiliate or disaffiliate to/from a group of merchants dynamically, and without causing a security problem for other merchants and customers. Being this way, we have decided that an specific entity will be responsible of issuing electronic coupons for a set of merchants. Therefore, we have, at least, three kinds of actors: customers, merchants and the issuer.

We want to provide a multicoupon scheme because some merchants prefer that customers buy a set of coupons (better than single coupons) to establish long-term relationships with them. This way, customers are encouraged to spend all the coupons of the set. Even, sometimes, a deadline is established to obtain the benefits of the coupons. In order to increase flexibility we foresee two possible situations: electronic coupons that can be refund before a deadline, and electronic coupons without refund (with or without deadline to spend them). The refund process is a new procedure that cannot be found in previous solutions. Some other processes are involved in the use of coupons (this kind

of processes can be found in all previous solutions). The claim process is necessary when the issuer and the merchant are not the same entity (we only find this process in [10, 11]). The redeem process can be found in all previous solutions but only one previous solution allows a multi-redeem process, although it is an useful process for efficiency purposes, as we will explain in our proposal.

Some merchants want that multicoupons meet the unsplitability requirement. It is to say, a customer cannot share electronic coupons from a booklet with another customer. In order to establish a long-term relationship with customers, merchants wish their multicoupons to be unsplitable [7]. This way a multicoupon cannot be shared among different customers. If a multicoupon is unsplitable, the customer will not be able to transfer coupons to another customer, or in the case she is allowed to do it then she must give all her coupons to the receiver. The unsplitability requirement can be classified as full or weak [8]. On one hand, in weak unsplitability (or all-or-nothing sharing) a customer must give the whole multicoupon to the receiver and she risks losing every remaining coupon on it. On the other hand, full unsplitability implies that the customer who shares a coupon with another customer cannot use any other coupon until the second customer provides some information to the first one.

So far we have highlighted merchant desires, but we also have to deal with customer desires, and privacy is especially important. Users want to maintain the same degree of privacy in the electronic version as in the paper version. So, confidentiality of transactions, unlinkability of uses, and anonymity have to be achieved. Moreover, we do not forget some common security requirements that our solution has to meet, and that all previous solutions satisfy, such as unforgeability and coupon reuse avoidance.

Contribution. We propose a complete scheme for multicoupon to be used in a multi-merchant scenario. Customers can spend different coupons of the multicoupon at different merchants affiliated to an issuer. The proposal builds unlikable and anonymous multicoupons, since nobody can determine who spends a coupon from a specific multicoupon and where these coupons are being spent. Therefore, a high degree of privacy is achieved for honest customers. Basic security requirements for merchants and issuers are met. Merchants are protected in front of possible customer misbehavior. If a customer tries to reuse or to forge a coupon (at the same or different merchants), her anonymity will be revoked. This measure is the key point to discourage customers from detaching an electronic coupon from a booklet. Similarly, the scheme provides measures against dishonest behavior from merchants, allowing the revocation of the merchant affiliation. All of these security requirements are proved by formal analysis.

We show by a analytic evaluation that our proposal enhances efficiency and flexibility in relation to the previous solution that deals with the multi-merchant scenario. This efficiency improvement comes from the fact that the scheme is based on lightweight cryptographic operations and allows to redeem and claim one or more coupons during the same run of the protocol. Meanwhile, the flexibility refers to the fact that the customer and the issuer can agree on the value and the number of coupons of each multicoupon, and merchants can join and leave the affiliation without reducing the security of the multicoupon scheme.

Organization. This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we give an overview of the scenario considered in this paper, describing the security model and the considered security requirements of our multicoupon scheme. In Section 3 we review the related work. We present the needed cryptographic background in Section 4. In Section 5 we outline how our proposal works and we define the structure and the life cycle of multicoupons. The full specification of protocols and data flows of our proposal are explained in Section 6. We provide a formal analysis of the security requirements in Section 7, and an efficiency comparison in Section 8. Finally, in Section 9 we conclude the paper.

2. OVERVIEW: SCENARIOS AND SECURITY MODEL

In this section, we present the scenario that we are dealing for this paper, the entities involved and their role in the multicoupon scenario. Moreover, we describe the security model along with the definition of the considered security requirements.

2.1. Multicoupon Scenario

As defined in the introduction section, we consider three entities: issuer, merchants and customers. So, based on the involved entities and the relationship among them, we define two types of scenarios that we have identified in the previous proposals. This will help to clarify the differences between our proposal and the existing ones, and to understand the need for new security measures.

- *Single-merchant.* This scenario involves many customers and a single merchant. That is, one merchant is in charge of the issuance, distribution and validation of multicoupons for the services that he offers to customers. Therefore, a customer can only use coupons at the merchant who issued them [5, 6, 7, 8, 9]. In this case, the issuer and the merchant are the same entity, so security is controlled by the merchant since he is responsible for issuing and validating coupons. Thus, he has all the information about the list of issued and already used coupons.

- *Multi-merchant.* As in the single-merchant scenario many customers can use multicoupons at one merchant, but in this case, in contrast to single-merchant scenario, a customer can also use the same multicoupon at different merchants [10, 11]. In this context, a merchant can accept coupons issued by another entity (another merchant or an issuer). Therefore, the security of the scheme must take into account that the merchant validating the multicoupon must have enough and valid information to verify the coupons presented by customers. This scenario allows attracting more customers to merchants. In addition, customers and merchants obtain greater benefits.

The scenario considered in this paper can be classified as a multi-merchant scenario where the issuer is the only entity in charge to issue multicoupons to customers, and merchants are the entities that accept and verify multicoupons. Moreover, a merchant could accept multicoupons issued by different issuers, but merchants should have an agreement with those issuers before accepting their multicoupons. In our scenario, a new entity called group manager, has been introduced to provide anonymity to the customers. This entity will be able to revoke the anonymity if it is required, as we will explain in §5.

2.2. Security Model

In the rest of this section we present a security framework based on the adversarial actions that can be performed by the entities involved in the multicoupon scenario. We follow a security model description similar to other authors [7, 9, 10]). We begin by defining the algorithms and protocols available to both honest and adversarial entities. An adversary is a probabilistic polynomial time algorithm (hereinafter p.p.t. algorithm) \mathcal{A} , which can play the role of either customers or merchants, so \mathcal{A} can interact with the other entities through a set of algorithms and protocols.

Finally, and based on the later description, we define the security requirements.

DEFINITION 2.1. (*Multicoupon Scheme*). *A multicoupon scheme (MC-2D) for an affiliation of merchants ($\mathcal{M} \in \{\mathcal{M}_0 \cdots \mathcal{M}_m\}$), a set of customers ($\mathcal{C} \in \{\mathcal{C}_0 \cdots \mathcal{C}_n\}$), an issuer (\mathcal{I}) and a group manager (\mathcal{G}), consists of a set of algorithms and protocols: $\{\text{GMSetup}, \text{PBSSetup}, \text{GMRegistration}, \text{Issue}, \text{MultiRedeem}, \text{Affiliation}, \text{Disaffiliation}, \text{Claim}, \text{and Refund}\}$.*

These algorithms and protocols are specified as follows:

- **GMSetup.** It is a probabilistic algorithm executed by \mathcal{G} taking as inputs the security parameter \mathcal{K} and the size \mathcal{N} of the group of users. It outputs a group public key (pk^G) and up to \mathcal{N} group member private keys $\{sk_{\mathcal{C}_i}^G\}_{i=0}^{\mathcal{N}-1}$.
- **PBSSetup.** It is a probabilistic algorithm executed by all parties (but \mathcal{G}) taking as input the security parameter \mathcal{K} . It outputs an RSA key pair (pk_p, sk_p) , where p denotes the corresponding party.
- **Affiliation.** It is a deterministic and interactive protocol performed between \mathcal{I} and merchants interested to redeem multicoupons issued by \mathcal{I} , taking as input the merchant affiliation list (\mathcal{AL}) . It outputs an agreement between \mathcal{I} and each \mathcal{M} allowing (identified by $id_{\mathcal{M}}$) \mathcal{M} the ability to accept and claim multicoupons to \mathcal{I} . In addition, the merchant identifier ($id_{\mathcal{M}}$) is included on the affiliation list (\mathcal{AL}) .
- **Disaffiliation.** It can be either a non-interactive algorithm or an interactive protocol. As non-interactive algorithm, it is performed by \mathcal{I} as a result of a merchant misbehaviour. It outputs both the merchant revocation list updated ($id_{\mathcal{M}}$ is included on the affiliation revocation list (\mathcal{ARL})), and the merchant affiliation list updated ($id_{\mathcal{M}}$ is deleted from the affiliation list (\mathcal{AL})). As interactive protocol, it is performed between the \mathcal{I} and a merchant wanting to leave the affiliation. In this case, it outputs the merchant affiliation list updated.
- **GMRegistration.** It is a deterministic and interactive protocol between \mathcal{G} and customers taking as inputs the identity of \mathcal{C} and returning to \mathcal{C} a group key pair $(pk^G, sk_{\mathcal{C}}^G)$. As a result, \mathcal{G} obtains the link between \mathcal{C} 's identity and her group member private key. If something fails, \mathcal{G} outputs an error message.
- **Issue.** It is a deterministic and interactive protocol between \mathcal{I} and \mathcal{C} . \mathcal{I} takes as inputs its RSA private key $(sk_{\mathcal{I}})$ and \mathcal{C} uses as input the \mathcal{I} 's RSA public key $(pk_{\mathcal{I}})$. \mathcal{I} and \mathcal{C} agree on some common information containing the value and the number of coupons within a multicoupon, together with some timestamps τ to limit when each algorithm can be executed. At the end of the protocol, \mathcal{C} obtains a multicoupon, denoted as MC^{2D} , whose identifier is hidden to \mathcal{I} due to the use of a partially blind signature scheme. If something fails, \mathcal{I} outputs an error message. The issuer outputs its view $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{I}}^{\text{Issue}}$ of the protocol.
- **Multiredeem.** It is a deterministic and interactive protocol executed between \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{M} . \mathcal{C} takes as inputs her MC^{2D} and her group key pair $(pk^G, sk_{\mathcal{C}}^G)$. \mathcal{M} uses as inputs his private key $(sk_{\mathcal{M}})$ and the group public key (pk^G) . Then, \mathcal{C} releases a list of coupons \mathcal{L}_R group signed using her group key pair in exchange of the requested good or service. Thus, at the end of the algorithm, \mathcal{M} obtains a list \mathcal{L}_R of coupons from \mathcal{C} . If something fails, \mathcal{M} outputs an error message. The merchant outputs its view $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}}^{\text{Multiredeem}}$ of the protocol.

- **Claim.** It is a deterministic and interactive protocol between \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{I} . \mathcal{M} uses as inputs the list of received coupons from customers (\mathcal{L}_R) and its private key ($sk_{\mathcal{M}}$). \mathcal{I} takes as inputs his public key ($pk_{\mathcal{I}}$) and the list of previously received coupons from affiliated merchants. At the end of the protocol, \mathcal{I} allows \mathcal{M} to deposit the value of the claimed coupons \mathcal{L}_R or outputs an error message if something fails. The issuer outputs its view $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{I}}^{\text{Claim}}$ of the protocol.
- **Refund.** It is a deterministic and interactive protocol between \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{I} . \mathcal{C} uses the list of coupons not yet redeemed ($\mathcal{L}_{\bar{R}}$) and her private key ($sk_{\mathcal{C}}$). As in the **Claim** algorithm, \mathcal{I} takes the same parameters as input. At the end of the protocol, \mathcal{C} obtains a refund of her unused and not yet redeemed coupons or an error message if something fails. The issuer outputs its view $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{I}}^{\text{Refund}}$ of the protocol.

DEFINITION 2.2. (Correctness). *If an honest customer \mathcal{C} runs the **Issue** protocol with an honest \mathcal{I} , then \mathcal{C} obtains a signed and properly issued multicoupon from \mathcal{I} . If an honest \mathcal{C} executes the **Multiredeem** protocol with an honest \mathcal{M} using some valid coupons from a valid multicoupon, then \mathcal{M} always accepts them. If an honest \mathcal{M} runs the **Claim** protocol with an honest \mathcal{I} using a list of coupons from some valid multicoupons received from honest customers, then \mathcal{I} always accept this list if all the contained coupons are valid.*

Note that a valid coupon is a coupon properly obtained from a valid **Issue** protocol and it has not been previously redeemed.

2.3. Unforgeability

There is an intrinsic monetary value associated to any coupon, either explicitly or implicitly. Therefore, the system needs to be unforgeable.

From the point of view of both issuer and merchants, no coalition of customers should be able: to redeem more coupons than they have been rightfully issued, to self-issue new multicoupons or to modify their content. In this case, let an adversary \mathcal{A}_0 be a p.p.t. Turing Machine acting as a malicious customer or a coalition of them. \mathcal{A}_0 has all the public parameters needed to operate in the system, so:

- \mathcal{A}_0 can execute the **Issue** protocol with an honest issuer.
- \mathcal{A}_0 can execute the **Multiredeem** protocol with an honest merchant.

Let us consider a game 0, where \mathcal{A}_0 can legitimately obtain a multicoupon (MC^{2D}) composed by a set of valid single coupons. Then, \mathcal{A}_0 can execute the **Multiredeem** algorithm with an honest merchant using a coupon $\mathbf{c} \notin \text{MC}^{2D}$. Therefore, it is required that for an adversary \mathcal{A}_0 playing the game 0, the probability an

honest merchant accepts the **Multiredeem** protocol is negligible.

On the another hand, the issuer is also interested on that no coalition of merchants should be able to claim more coupons than they had been received by customers. In this case, let an adversary \mathcal{A}_1 be a p.p.t. Turing Machine acting as a malicious merchant or a coalition of them. \mathcal{A}_1 has all the public parameters needed to participate in the system, so:

- \mathcal{A}_1 can execute the **Multiredeem** protocol with honest customers.
- \mathcal{A}_1 can execute the **Claim** protocol with an honest issuer.

Let us consider a game 1, where \mathcal{A}_1 receives a list of coupons \mathcal{L}_R from honest customers. Let us define some counters: \mathcal{Z}_R as the number of coupons redeemed by honest customers; \mathcal{Z}_C as the number of coupons claimed by the adversary. Then, \mathcal{A}_1 can execute the **Claim** protocol transferring \mathcal{Z}_C coupons that is greater than \mathcal{Z}_R , i.e. $\mathcal{Z}_C > \mathcal{Z}_R$. Then, it is required that the probability for an adversary \mathcal{A}_1 , playing game 1, to claim more coupons than the number of coupons redeemed by honest customers during the **Multiredeem** algorithm, is negligible.

Note that, \mathcal{I} may issue as many coupons as he wants, and hence, unforgeability with a corrupted issuer would make no sense.

Formaly, the unforgeability property is defined as follows:

DEFINITION 2.3. (Unforgeability). *A multicoupon scheme is unforgeable if there is no p.p.t. adversary $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{A}_0, \mathcal{A}_1)$ that can win any game with non-negligible probability (in \mathcal{K}).*

2.4. Unlinkability

Customers want to protect their operations in the system in a sense that it should be infeasible for a merchant or a coalition of them to link a redeem procedure to the corresponding issue procedure where the multicoupon had been issued, or to link two different redeem procedures from the same customer using different MC^{2D} multicoupons. That is, it tries to know whether two prodecures have been made by a same customer no matters which is her identity [9].

On one hand, let an adversary \mathcal{A}_0 be a p.p.t. Turing Machine acting as a malicious merchant or a coalition of them. Assume that \mathcal{C}_0 (holds MC_0^{2D}) and \mathcal{C}_1 (holds MC_1^{2D}) have already executed at least one **Multiredeem** with the multicoupons they hold. Consequently, \mathcal{A}_0 has one view for each **Multiredeem** protocol run, i.e. $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{A}_0}^{\text{Multiredeem}_0}$ and $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{A}_0}^{\text{Multiredeem}_1}$. \mathcal{A}_0 has all the public parameters to be involved in the system, so:

- \mathcal{A}_0 can execute the **Multiredeem** protocol with honest customers.

Let us consider a game 0, where \mathcal{A}_0 outputs secretly and randomly a bit $b = \{0,1\}$. At some point, \mathcal{A}_0 executes a **Multiredeem** protocol with the honest customer b (\mathcal{C}_b) who owns the multicoupon used during the **Multiredeem**, and \mathcal{A}_0 outputs a bit $b' = \{0,1\}$. Then, we require that for every adversary playing the game, the advantage in the success probability that \mathcal{C}_b and $\mathcal{C}_{b'}$ are the same customer, is at most negligible. In fact, we require that the probability for an adversary to win the game is not better than a random toss of the coin.

On the other hand, let an adversary \mathcal{A}_1 be a p.p.t. Turing Machine acting as a malicious merchant or a coalition of them. Moreover, suppose a corrupted issuer who provides \mathcal{A}_1 the complete view of a previously executed **Issue** protocol. \mathcal{A}_1 has all the public parameters to be involved in the system, so:

- \mathcal{A}_1 can execute the **Multiredeem** protocol with honest customers.

Let us consider a game 1, where \mathcal{A}_1 obtains two views from two **Issue** protocols, i.e. $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{I}}^{Issue_0}$ and $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{I}}^{Issue_1}$, from a corrupted issuer. Suddenly, \mathcal{A}_1 outputs a bit $b' = \{0,1\}$. Then, \mathcal{A}_1 executes a **Multiredeem** protocol with the honest customer b who owns the multicoupon contained in $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{I}}^{Issue_b}$. Finally, \mathcal{A}_1 outputs another bit $b' = \{0,1\}$. As in the game 0, we require that for every adversary playing the game, the advantage in the success probability that $\mathcal{C}_b = \mathcal{C}_{b'}$ is at most negligible.

DEFINITION 2.4. (Unlinkability). *The multicoupon scheme is 2D-unlinkable if there is no p.p.t. adversary $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{A}_0, \mathcal{A}_1)$ that can win any game with non-negligible linkability advantage over random guess (in \mathcal{K}).*

2.5. Anonymity of Customers

Customers interested in using coupons do not want to reveal their identity to perform actions in the system. So, customers want to be anonymous, i.e. customers should be able to obtain and redeem coupons without revealing any information about their real identity. Neither the issuer, who issues coupons to customers, nor merchants, who accept the coupons from customers, must not be able to obtain information concerning the identity of the customers.

Consider an adversary \mathcal{A}_0 as a p.p.t. Turing Machine playing a game 0 and acting as a malicious issuer. \mathcal{A} has all the parameters needed to be involved in the system, so:

- \mathcal{A}_0 can execute the **Issue** protocol with honest customers.

Similarly, consider an adversary \mathcal{A}_1 playing a game 1 and acting as a malicious merchant and having all the parameters to be involved in the system, so:

- \mathcal{A}_1 can execute the **Multiredeem** protocol with honest customers.

At some point of game 0 (game 1, resp.), \mathcal{A}_0 (\mathcal{A}_1 , resp.) tries to infer the real identity of the customer using all data contained in each protocol view (either $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{A}_0}^{Issue}$ or $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{A}_1}^{Multiredeem}$, resp.). Then, it is required that the probability for an adversary (playing any of the games) to obtain the real identity of a customer is negligible.

DEFINITION 2.5. (Anonymity). *The multicoupon scheme is anonymous if there is no p.p.t. adversary $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{A}_0, \mathcal{A}_1)$ that can win the anonymity games obtaining the identity of an honest customer when she is performing actions in the system (either issue a multicoupon from the issuer or redeem a coupon from a merchant) with non-negligible probability (in \mathcal{K}).*

2.6. Coupon Reuse Avoidance

The system must prevent, or at least detect, that neither a customer has redeemed the same coupon more than once nor a merchant has claimed the same coupon more than once. It is clear that we cannot prevent entities making copies of coupons but we must assure that only one of them will be given as valid.

Formally, we can define an adversary \mathcal{A}_0 as a p.p.t. Turing Machine playing a game 0 with the role of a malicious customer or a coalition of them. \mathcal{A}_0 has all the parameters needed to be involved in the system, so:

- \mathcal{A}_0 can execute the **Issue** protocol with an honest issuer.
- \mathcal{A}_0 can execute the **Multiredeem** protocol with honest merchants.

At some point of the game 0, \mathcal{A}_0 tries to redeem the same coupon twice or more times with either the same merchant or different merchants, using the **Multiredeem** protocol.

Similarly, let define an adversary \mathcal{A}_1 who plays a game 1 with the role of a malicious merchant or a coalition of them. \mathcal{A}_1 has all the parameters needed to be involved in the system, so:

- \mathcal{A}_1 can execute the **Multiredeem** protocol with an honest customer.
- \mathcal{A}_1 can execute the **Claim** protocol with an honest issuer.

At some point of the game 1, \mathcal{A}_1 tries to claim the same coupon twice or more times to the issuer, using the **Claim** protocol.

Then, for each game we require that the probability for each adversary to redeem (or claim) a coupon already redeemed (or claimed) without the honest merchant (or the issuer) detecting and avoiding the reuse is negligible. Note that in every case, the system allows the anonymity revocation of the misbehaving party and revealing her identity (see definition 2.7).

DEFINITION 2.6. (*Coupon reuse avoidance*). The multicoupon scheme allows detecting and avoiding coupon reuse if no p.p.t. adversary $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{A}_0, \mathcal{A}_1)$ can win any game using two coupons, i.e. \mathbf{c} and \mathbf{c}' from the same multicoupon MC^{2D} , where $\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{c}'$, without the verifier (either merchant or issuer) detecting it, with non-negligible probability (in \mathcal{K}).

2.7. Anonymity Revocation of Misbehaving Customers

Although the anonymity of customers is desired, the scheme must provide a mechanism to reveal the identity of customers when they misbehave, i.e. when a customer tries either to use a fake coupon or to reuse a coupon already redeemed, her anonymity must be revoked. It should be also possible to revoke the anonymity of a malicious customer trying to unfairly blame an honest customer.

Let us consider an adversary \mathcal{A} as a p.p.t. Turing Machine acting as a malicious customer, a coalition of them or probably also colluding with a malicious merchant. \mathcal{A} has all the parameters required to operate in the system, so:

- \mathcal{A} can execute the `Multiredeem` protocol with honest merchants.

At some point of the game, \mathcal{A} tries to execute the `Multiredeem` protocol with an honest merchant using either a forged coupon (see definition 2.3) or a coupon already used in a previous `Multiredeem` instance (see definition 2.6). Then, through the use of an anonymity revocation mechanism, the anonymity of the cheater should be revoked and her identification should be also correct even \mathcal{A} tries to blame an honest customer (non-frameability). So, it is required that the probability for the adversary to be not identified by the revocation mechanism, after either a forging or a coupon reuse attempt, should be negligible.

DEFINITION 2.7. (*Anonymity revocation of misbehaving customers*). The multicoupon scheme allows the anonymity revocation and the correct identification of malicious customers if there is no p.p.t. adversary \mathcal{A} that can win the game with non-negligible probability (in \mathcal{K}).

2.8. Disaffiliation of Merchants

Every merchant who wants to accept and claim multicoupons issued by the issuer, must be affiliated to that issuer. Then, the issuer assigns an unique merchant identifier ($id_{\mathcal{M}}$) to each affiliated merchant, and adds this identifier to the affiliation list (\mathcal{AL}). Similarly to the affiliation, the system must provide a secure disaffiliation when merchants leave it. We define two types of disaffiliation: voluntarily or forced.

- *Voluntarily disaffiliation*. An honest merchant decides on his own, by some reasons, that he does

not want to belong the affiliation anymore. Issuer removes merchant from the affiliation list.

- *Forced disaffiliation*. The scheme must provide measures against dishonest behavior of merchants. For example, assuming an honest customer, a merchant could misbehave similarly to a customer, that is, using a fake coupon or reusing a coupon received from a customer. When a merchant misbehaves, the issuer should be able to revoke the affiliation of this dishonest merchant adding him to the affiliation revocation list (\mathcal{ARL}) and also removing him from the affiliation list (\mathcal{AL}).

In both cases, when a merchant leaves the system, i.e. he leaves the affiliation with the issuer, the security of the multicoupon scheme must not be compromised. So, the issuer and merchants cannot share sensitive information about customers. Moreover, once a merchant has left the affiliation, he can no longer obtain benefits from the issuer, for example, changing coupons for money.

We can define an adversary \mathcal{A} who plays a game with the role of a malicious merchant (merchant not affiliated to the issuer) or a coalition of them. \mathcal{A} has all the parameters needed to be involved in the system, so:

- \mathcal{A} can execute the `Multiredeem` protocol with customers.
- \mathcal{A} can execute the `Claim` protocol with an honest issuer.

Let us consider a game, where \mathcal{A} can execute the `Multiredeem` algorithm with customers obtaining a set of valid coupons. Later, \mathcal{A} tries to claim these valid coupons using the `Claim` protocol. Then, we require that the probability for a not affiliated adversary ($\mathcal{A} \notin \mathcal{AL}$) to claim a coupon without the honest issuer detecting and avoiding it is negligible.

DEFINITION 2.8. (*Disaffiliation of merchants*). The multicoupon scheme is secure against merchants disaffiliation either forced by a proved misbehavior or voluntarily by the merchant decision, if there is no p.p.t. adversary \mathcal{A} that can win the game, obtaining coupons from honest customers and then achieving the associated benefits of these coupons from the issuer, with non-negligible probability (in \mathcal{K}).

2.9. Unsplittability Protection

We can find two definitions about unsplittability. On one hand, *weak unsplittability*, as defined in [8], requires that whether a customer wants to share some coupons of a multicoupon with another entity, she must provide secret information related to that multicoupon. Thus, it is designed to discourage sharing. On the other hand, *strong unsplittability* requires that whether a customer gives a single coupon to another customer, the first customer cannot use any other coupon until the second customer provides some information to the first one

[10]. In both cases (*weak* and *strong unsplitability*) customers sharing coupons must trust each other.

In our scheme, we take into account *weak unsplitability*. In this case, let an adversary \mathcal{A}_0 be a p.p.t. Turing Machine acting as a customer or a coalition of customers. \mathcal{A}_0 can share a set of coupons from her legitimately issued multicoupon MC^{2D} , so:

- \mathcal{A}_0 can execute the **Issue** protocol with an honest issuer.
- \mathcal{A}_0 can execute the **Multiredeem** protocol with honest merchants.

Let us consider a game 0, where \mathcal{A}_0 obtains a valid multicoupon (MC^{2D}) from the issuer. Then, \mathcal{A}_0 extracts a list \mathcal{L}_s of valid coupons from a legitimately issued multicoupon MC^{2D} , and gives this \mathcal{L}_s to an honest customer \mathcal{C}_0 . Then, \mathcal{A}_0 can execute the **Multiredeem** algorithm with an honest merchant using a coupon $\mathbf{c} \in \mathcal{L}_s$.

Hence, for an adversary \mathcal{A}_0 playing the game 0, the probability that \mathcal{C}_0 can be falsely accused of coupon reuse is non-negligible.

Similarly, consider an adversary \mathcal{A}_1 be a p.p.t. Turing Machine acting as a customer or a coalition of customers. \mathcal{A}_1 can receive a set of coupons from another customer \mathcal{C}_1 who has a legitimately issued multicoupon MC^{2D} , so:

- \mathcal{A}_1 can execute a **Multiredeem** protocol with honest merchants.

Let us consider a game 1, where \mathcal{A}_1 receives a list \mathcal{L}_s of valid coupons \mathbf{c} from \mathcal{C}_1 . Then, \mathcal{A}_1 can execute the **Multiredeem** algorithm with an honest merchant using a coupon $\mathbf{c} \notin \mathcal{L}_s$, but $\mathbf{c} \in \text{MC}^{2D}$.

Therefore, for an adversary \mathcal{A}_1 playing the game 1, the probability that \mathcal{A}_1 could cause \mathcal{C}_1 to be falsely accused of coupon reuse is non-negligible.

Protection against splitting was defined in [5] and we have adapted it to our scheme as follows:

DEFINITION 2.9. (Unsplitability Protection). *Customers are discouraged to either split and share an N_j -redeemable multicoupon into (disjoint) s_i -redeemable shares with $\sum_i s_i \leq N_j$, or receive a s_i -redeemable shares, without customers trust each other, since an honest customer is at risk of being unfairly accused of coupon reuse (with non-negligible probability in \mathcal{K}).*

3. RELATED WORK

As we already pointed out in the introduction, there are several proposals to provide security to multicoupons. We analyze these proposals considering two main aspects of multicoupon schemes: functionalities and security properties. Table 1 summarizes the set of features and properties of all the reviewed proposals.

Regarding functionalities, all the analyzed solutions [5, 6, 7, 8, 9] provide the basic protocols required

for operating with multicoupons (issue and redeem) in single-merchant scenarios. However, further procedures are needed for more general scenarios, such as claim and refund. On one hand, the claim protocol is required when the entity who issues coupons and the entity who exchanges them with the customer for goods or services are not the same entity. This is the case for a multi-merchant scenario like the proposed in [10, 11]. On the other hand, a refund protocol allows customers to recover from the issuer the value of a list of already issued coupons but not used yet.

Even though the redeem process is supported by all the proposals, solutions for multicoupons should provide mechanisms to allow redeeming more than one single-coupon within the same redeem process. This process is called multi-redemption and it is an interesting process for flexibility and efficiency purposes. However, the vast majority of analyzed solutions require executing the redeem process as many times as individual coupons are provided. To the best of our knowledge, this process is only supported by [7, 13].

As mentioned in [5, 13] a privacy protecting coupon system should at least provide the property of *weak unsplitability*. The solutions presented in [5, 6] allow *weak unsplitability* while the schemes in [8, 9, 10] obtain *strong unsplitability*. Instead, the proposal in [7] provides customer with the possibility to detach a coupon from a multicoupon and transfer it to another customer, but in this case, the issuer entity must be involved in the transfer process.

Concerning security, multicoupon solutions should consider the customer privacy, and the detection and prevention of fraudulent use of multicoupons. Almost all the analyzed schemes accomplish with these requirements [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10], but although these schemes deal with customer anonymity, they do not take into account the possibility to revoke the anonymity of the customer when she makes a fraudulent use of coupons, or to provide confidentiality of the data exchange between the two edges of the communication. However, the main drawback of the vast majority of multicoupons schemes is that they are designed for *single-merchant* scenarios [5, 6, 7, 8, 9], so security is controlled by the merchant, since he is responsible for issuing and validating coupons. But, these kind of schemes reduce the use scope of multicoupons because customers can only interact with the merchant who issued the multicoupons.

The above limitation was partially solved by [10, 11] allowing a *multi-merchant* scenario. In the scheme proposed in [10], customers obtain multicoupons from any merchant within the same federation and customers can spend the coupons at any federated merchant. The federation is an association of merchants where all merchants share a key pair (public and private), and each merchant has a different private key to sign coupons. However, the merchant who receives a coupon, previously issued by another merchant, must

TABLE 1. Multicoupons solutions - A comparative analysis

	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]	[9]	[10]	[11]	Our proposal
Scenario	SM	SM	SM	SM	SM	MM	MM	MM
Issue	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Redeem	single	single	multi	single	single	single	multi	multi
Claim	-	-	-	-	-	✓	✓	✓
Refund	-	-	-	-	-	-	optional	optional
Unsplitting	weak	weak	-	strong	strong	strong	-	weak
Unforgeability	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Coupon reuse avoidance	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Unlinkability	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Customer anonymity	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Confidentiality	-	-	-	-	-	-	✓	✓
Merchant Disaffiliation	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	✓
Revocation of Customer's Anonymity	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	✓
Revocation of Merchant's Affiliation	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	✓

✓YES, -NO

SM- single-merchant MM- multi-merchant

find and contact with the original issuer in order to recover the applied discount. Moreover, the merchants must share the same federation private key and a common database where data about issued and already used coupons must be updated by merchants. So, when a merchant leaves the federation, the shared private key and the shared data can be compromised, opening a serious security problem. In addition, the multicoupon scheme should provide measures to expel dishonest merchants from the federation. This is a critical security issue unresolved by [10].

The scheme proposed in [11] solves the shared data issue of [10], however merchants could obtain coupons from honest customers and those coupons could be used by other misbehaving customers in collusion with the dishonest merchants. Besides the fact that an honest customer could lose her valid coupons, she could be also accused by a dishonest party or a collusion of dishonest parties of coupon reuse. Moreover, this issue entails problems about the fairness of the involved protocols.

Therefore, new mechanisms are needed to obtain a multicoupon scheme more secure and efficient in a *multi-merchant* scenario.

4. CRYPTOGRAPHIC BACKGROUND

In this section, we briefly review a few cryptographic techniques which will be used in our proposal as building blocks.

4.1. Group Signature

The aim of group signatures is to provide anonymity to the signers who belong to a group of users. This type of signature provides anonymity for signers because any member of the group can sign messages, but the resulting signature keeps secret the identity of the signer. Some systems define a third party who can trace the signature or revoke its anonymity, using a special trapdoor. After a review of several group signature schemes, we decided to use the short group signature

proposal made by [14]. This scheme allows generating short group signatures whose length is under 200 bytes, and with, approximately, the same level of security as a regular RSA signature of the same length. The security of the scheme is based on the Strong Diffie-Hellman (SDH) assumption in groups with a bilinear map [15].

Next, we explain briefly the involved parties and the procedures defined in [14] which will be used in our proposal. The scheme considers the following three parties:

- *Group Manager*. It is the only party who can generate keys and trace signatures.
- *Signer*. It is the party who signs messages using the key pair issued by the group manager.
- *Verifier*. It is the party who can verify group signed messages.

The scheme is concisely defined by the following four procedures:

- *KeyGen^G(n)*. This randomized algorithm takes as input the number of members of the group (n), and outputs a group public key (pk^G), a private key of the group manager (sk_G^G) and n user private keys ($sk_1^G \dots sk_n^G$).
- *Sign_u^G(pk^G, sk_u^G, m)*. Given a group public key pk^G , a user private key sk_u^G and a message m of an arbitrary length, this procedure outputs a group signature σ .
- *Verify^G(pk^G, m, σ)*. Given a group public key pk^G , a message m and a group signature σ , it verifies that σ is a valid group signature.
- *Open_G^G(pk^G, sk_G^G, m, σ)*. This procedure is used by the Group Manager to trace a signature to the identity of the signer. It takes a group public key pk^G , the group manager's private key sk_G^G , a message m and a signature σ , and it recovers and outputs the identity of the signer.

FIGURE 1. Our proposed scenario. Entities relationship and protocol flow.

4.2. Partially Blind Signature

A partially blind signature (\mathcal{PBS} for short) is related to the concept of blind signatures [16] which plays a central role in cryptographic protocols where the user anonymity is required, such as in electronic cash or electronic voting schemes. Blind signatures are used by a requester who blinds some information to the signer in order to hide it. But common blind signature presents an important shortcoming because the signer has not any control over the blind signed parameters. \mathcal{PBS} allows the signer to introduce some common information, previously agreed between the signer and the requester, in the blind signature. This is a generalization of blind signature since the common blind signature is a special case of a \mathcal{PBS} where the common information is null.

In our proposal we use the scheme defined in [17], which is based on RSA, because it is easy to implement and it is also efficient. In that scheme, the *requester* (the user who requests the partially blind signature) and the *signer* (the entity who signs the request) interact through five phases:

- $Init^{\mathcal{PBS}}$. In this stage, the *signer* deploys a RSA key pair, publishes his public key and picks a hash function.
- $Request^{\mathcal{PBS}}$. The *requester* asks for a partially blind signature over some hidden data that she sends to the *signer* together with some public common information previously agreed between them.
- $Sign^{\mathcal{PBS}}$. The *signer* signs the data received from the *requester*.
- $Extract^{\mathcal{PBS}}$. The *requester* unblinds the received data from the *signer* and she obtains the partially blind signature.
- $Verify^{\mathcal{PBS}}$. Anyone can verify the partially blind signature applying this procedure.

4.3. Hash Chains

A hash chain ($w_N \cdots w_0$) is defined as a set of values where w_N is a random value used as seed of the hash

chain, and the rest of values are generated applying iteratively a cryptographic hash function \mathcal{H} over w_N up to the value w_0 , called root, i.e., $\mathcal{H}(w_N) = w_{N-1}$, $\mathcal{H}(w_{N-1}) = w_{N-2}$, ..., $\mathcal{H}(w_1) = w_0$. Then, the verification of a chained element w_i ($N \geq i \geq 1$) is done applying i times the hash function \mathcal{H} over it, checking the relation $\mathcal{H}^i(w_i) \stackrel{?}{=} w_0$, where the verifier should know the root value w_0 .

The key feature of hash chains is that if a value w_i is provided, it is not feasible to find another w_j where $j > i$ so that $\mathcal{H}^{j-i}(w_j) = w_i$.

5. MC-2D: A MULTICOUPON SCHEME

In this section we present a multicoupon scheme, that we call $\mathcal{MC-2D}$. This scheme accomplishes all the security requirements for a *multi-merchant* scenario (see §2) where merchants are affiliated to an issuer entity. Therefore, a merchant does not need a prior relationship with other affiliated merchants nor share any information, and where honest entities are protected in front of dishonest parties, solving the problems of previous solutions.

5.1. Our Proposal in a Nutshell

As explained in §2, the involved entities in our scenario are: issuer (\mathcal{I}), merchants (\mathcal{M}), customers (\mathcal{C}) and group manager (\mathcal{G}). The latter is a trusted third party that comes from the group signature primitive, explained in §4.1.

Figure 1 draws the protocol flow and the interactions among all the involved parties. As an initial assumption, we consider the use of a secure channel between the two edges of the communication in order to provide data confidentiality to the involved parties. To initialize, \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{I} must execute a setup procedure in order to receive requests from the other parties.

On one hand, each \mathcal{M} interested in accepting multicoupons issued by \mathcal{I} must affiliate to \mathcal{I} . This is a simple step because the only thing they do is a contract agreement. No sensitive data is shared among \mathcal{I} and merchants, so they can join and leave the affiliation

FIGURE 2. Life cycle of multicoupon.

without any security trouble neither for customers nor for \mathcal{I} .

On the other hand, \mathcal{C} should register to \mathcal{G} in order to receive a group key pair which will be used by \mathcal{C} to hide her real identity when she acquires goods or services (henceforth services) at merchants. At this point, \mathcal{G} links a group key pair with \mathcal{C} 's identity, allowing further anonymity revocation if she misbehaves.

Since this moment, \mathcal{C} can request to \mathcal{I} a multicoupon (*Issue protocol*). After the issuing process, \mathcal{C} is ready to (multi-)redeem a set of coupons from the received multicoupon at any \mathcal{M} in exchange of a service (*Multi-redeem protocol*). When \mathcal{M} has a list of received coupons from customers, he can exchange it for a money transfer to his account balance (*Claim protocol*). It is important to note that the last three protocols allow sending several coupons using a single transaction, so it increases the protocol efficiency, as we will prove in §8.

Finally, a refund procedure has been designed to allow \mathcal{C} to request \mathcal{I} a reimbursement of her unused coupons whether she is no more interested in the use of her multicoupon. This procedure is designed to be optional and its application will depend on the agreement of the involved parties and the offered service.

In Figure 2 we define some time values used to manage the coupons life cycle in order to limit when each party can execute each protocol. This definition is also useful from the point of view of the efficiency because when a multicoupon is not usable anymore, parties can erase the related data. These time values are included inside the multicoupon together with other parameters that will be explained below.

5.2. The Multicoupon Structure

Our scheme is designed around a general multicoupon structure, called MC^{2D} , which is made up of two elements (see Figure 3):

1. MC_ω : the set of multicoupons generated applying hash chain operations.
2. $\text{MC}_{\mathcal{P}\mathcal{B}\mathcal{S}}$: the partially blind signature over the list of identifiers of each multicoupon.

The MC_ω element holds a number J of multicoupons, each one of them containing a chained list of single coupons denoted as $\mathbf{c}_j(m)$, where m ($1 \leq m \leq N_j$) is the coupon position within a multicoupon j , and N_j is the number of coupons of the multicoupon j . These multicoupons are obtained applying the hash

chain procedure over a random seed identifier $\omega_{N_j,j}$ (the first element of the hash chain) up to the final element of the chain (see §4.3) which is called the multicoupon identifier ($\omega_{0,j}$). As it can be seen in the Figure 3, each coupon contains two fields ($\mathbf{c}_j(m) = [\omega_{i+1,j}, \omega_{i,j}]$): proof information ($\omega_{i+1,j}$) and payment information ($\omega_{i,j}$). These two fields are related by a hash operation ($\mathcal{H}(\omega_{i+1,j}) = \omega_{i,j}$), so that the proof information piece proves that the previous payment information belongs to the same multicoupon from an issued MC^{2D} , thanks to the use of hash chain properties.

The $\text{MC}_{\mathcal{P}\mathcal{B}\mathcal{S}}$ element is generated by the cooperation of both \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{I} when the MC^{2D} is issued. This element will be used by \mathcal{C} to prove that she has a MC^{2D} properly issued by \mathcal{I} . The partially blind signature contains three fields: the common information (Γ), the verification data (Δ, Ω) and the multicoupon identifiers list from each multicoupon ($[\omega_{0,j}]_{j=1}^J$).

The common information field $\Gamma = (\mathcal{I}_{id}, s_{id}, [(N_j, v_j)]_{j=1}^J, \tau_{exp}, \tau_c, \tau_r)$ is an array of public data previously published by \mathcal{I} , which describes each of the offered services. There are some mandatory parameters and some of them are optional depending on the provided service and its features. The list of parameters is as follows:

- \mathcal{I}_{id} . An optional identification of the \mathcal{I} who issues the MC^{2D} .
- s_{id} . An optional identifier about the target service.
- N_j . It is the number of coupons within a single multicoupon j .
- $[(N_j, v_j)]_{j=1}^J$. This matrix contains J rows where each of them specifies the number of coupons and their value for each multicoupon j , where $1 \leq j \leq J$. Note that all coupons inside each multicoupon j have the same value v_j , but coupons from another multicoupon could have different value.
- τ_{exp} . It is the time up to \mathcal{C} can redeem her coupons to merchants.
- τ_c . It is the time up to \mathcal{M} can claim to \mathcal{I} the received coupons from customers.
- τ_r . If merchants and \mathcal{I} agree on providing the refund feature, this parameter indicates the time up to \mathcal{C} can ask \mathcal{I} for a refund of her unused coupons.

The verification field (Δ, Ω) contains data generated during the partially blind signing process which will be used to verify the signature. Finally, the last field contains the list of multicoupons identifiers ($[\omega_{0,j}]_{j=1}^J$). This data is hidden to \mathcal{I} when the $\text{MC}_{\mathcal{P}\mathcal{B}\mathcal{S}}$ is issued by means of the use of a partially blind signature scheme.

6. THE FULL SPECIFICATION OF THE MULTICOUPON PROPOSAL

Now we are going to define all the protocols in detail. Table 2 shows the notation used along the protocol

FIGURE 3. MC^{2D} structure composed by MC_ω and MC_{PBS} .

TABLE 2. Notation used in the protocol description.

Parameter	Description
$\mathcal{H}(x)$	One-way collision resistant hash function
$\mathcal{H}^i(x)$	$\mathcal{H}()$ applied i times iteratively
$\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{X}}(x)$	Signature over the element x made by party \mathcal{X}
$x \xleftarrow{R} \mathbb{Z}_r$ and $x \xleftarrow{R} \mathbb{Z}_n^*$	x randomly chosen from \mathbb{Z}_r or \mathbb{Z}_n^* sets
MC^{2D}	The structure of a multicoupon containing two elements $[MC_\omega, MC_{PBS}]$
MC_ω	Set of multicoupons containing a chained list of single coupons $\mathbf{c}_j(m)$
MC_{PBS}	Partially blind signature over root identifiers of MC_ω
$\mathbf{c}_j(m) = [\omega_{i+1,j}, \omega_{i,j}]$	A single coupon: proof information ($\omega_{i+1,j}$) and payment information ($\omega_{i,j}$)
$\mathcal{SG}_{\mathcal{C}}(x)$	Group signature over x generated by \mathcal{C} using $Sign_{\mathcal{C}}^G$ (see §4.1)
$\omega_{0,j} \parallel_{j=1}^J$	Concatenation of the J multicoupon identifiers in MC_ω
(e, n)	RSA public key of \mathcal{I}
(d, p, q)	RSA private key of \mathcal{I}
$id_{\mathcal{M}}$	Merchant's unique identifier in the affiliation
id_r	Unique identifier for a multi-redeem transaction

description.

6.1. System Setup

The system setup is divided into two parts: \mathcal{G} key deployment and \mathcal{I} setup.

- **\mathcal{G} key deployment.** \mathcal{G} executes the procedure $KeyGen^G$ as explained in §4.1 and outputs a group public key (pk^G), a group manager private key ($sk_{\mathcal{G}}^G$) and a predefined number of user private keys (sk_1^G, sk_2^G, \dots).
- **\mathcal{I} setup.** \mathcal{I} should deploy a RSA key pair in order to use the partially blind signature scheme using the procedure $Init^{PBS}$ described in §4.2.

6.2. Affiliation/Disaffiliation

The scheme requires that each merchant who is interested in receiving coupons issued by \mathcal{I} should affiliate to \mathcal{I} , signing an agreement. This agreement could consist on a list of terms and conditions. Without this affiliation, \mathcal{M} cannot execute the *claim protocol* to exchange a list of received coupons through a payment. At the end of the affiliation stage, \mathcal{I} will

assign an unique identifier ($id_{\mathcal{M}}$) to the merchant. With this information, \mathcal{I} can maintain a list of affiliated merchants.

The scheme distinguishes two kinds of disaffiliation, by merchant own decision or forced. In the first case, \mathcal{I} only need to remove the merchant from the affiliation list. In the latter case, in addition to remove the merchant from the affiliation list, \mathcal{I} keeps up an affiliation revocation list that can be useful if a merchant expelled from the affiliation tries to join the affiliation again in the future.

In any case, \mathcal{I} and merchants do not share sensitive information, since merchants only need to know \mathcal{I} 's public key (e, n) and group's public key (pk^G). Therefore, merchants can leave the affiliation from \mathcal{I} without causing security problems.

6.3. Group Manager Registration

Before \mathcal{C} can use a MC^{2D} from \mathcal{I} , she must register to \mathcal{G} in order to download a group key pair. \mathcal{G} authenticates \mathcal{C} using her digital certificate $Cert_{\mathcal{C}}$. So \mathcal{G} links an user private key $sk_{\mathcal{C}}^G$ to \mathcal{C} 's identity and sends her a group key pair ($pk^G, sk_{\mathcal{C}}^G$) and a digital certificate

$Cert_G$ (issued by a trusted authority) that authenticates the group public key (pk^G). This link is needed to revoke the customer's anonymity when she misbehaves. At this step, customers agree that their identity can be disclosed whether they are not honest or whether an authority (e.g. a judge) requires the revocation of the anonymity.

6.4. Issue Protocol

The *issue protocol* (Figure 4) involves \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{I} and allows the former to obtain an anonymous \mathbb{MC}^{2D} from the latter. It is an anonymous process because \mathcal{I} does not require any kind of user identification nor pseudonym. In addition, neither $\mathbb{MC}_{\mathcal{P}BS}$ nor \mathbb{MC}_ω contain data about \mathcal{C} 's identity. Moreover, thanks to the way we use a partially blind signature scheme, the list of multicoupons identifiers, denoted as $[\omega_{0,j}]_{j=1}^J$, is hidden from \mathcal{I} , so \mathcal{I} has no information about it, except that it is usable and properly issued. Thus, nobody (but \mathcal{G}) can trace \mathcal{C} 's activities.

The protocol starts when \mathcal{C} picks J random seed identifiers and using hash chains properties, she obtains \mathbb{MC}_ω , that is, J multicoupons containing each of them N_j coupons with v_j value. Then, she must choose and agree with \mathcal{I} on the public common information Γ (see §5.2). After that, \mathcal{C} blinds the concatenated list of multicoupon identifiers using a cryptographic hash function ($\mathcal{H}(\omega_{0,j} \|_{j=1}^J)$) and sends it, together with the common information, to \mathcal{I} .

After the execution of the *issue protocol*, on one hand \mathcal{C} acquires a $\mathbb{MC}_{\mathcal{P}BS}$, fully defined as $[\Gamma, (\Delta, \Omega), [\omega_{0,j}]_{j=1}^J]$, where Γ is the common information, (Δ, Ω) contains verification data and $[\omega_{0,j}]_{j=1}^J$ is the list of the multicoupons identifiers (see Figure 3). On the other hand, \mathcal{I} knows nothing about the \mathbb{MC}^{2D} but it is properly issued and ready to use on the multi-merchant environment.

The $\mathbb{MC}_{\mathcal{P}BS} = [\Gamma, (\Delta, \Omega), [\omega_{0,j}]_{j=1}^J]$ verification can be done applying a public equation that can be used by anyone who knows the \mathcal{I} 's RSA public key (e, n) and the $\mathbb{MC}_{\mathcal{P}BS}$ element. In order to do it, a verifier follows the *Verify $^{\mathcal{P}BS}$* (see §4.2) procedure checking if the following equation holds:

$$\Omega^e \stackrel{?}{\equiv} \mathcal{H}(\Gamma) \mathcal{H}(\omega_{0,j} \|_{j=1}^J)^2 (\Delta^2 + 1)^2 \pmod{n}$$

If the result is true, the verifier is convinced that the \mathbb{MC}^{2D} is properly issued and the \mathbb{MC}^{2D} is accepted. Otherwise, the verifier rejects the \mathbb{MC}^{2D} .

6.5. Multi-redeem Protocol

The *multi-redeem protocol* (Figure 5) is run between \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{M} . It is initiated by \mathcal{C} and it allows her to spend coupons from her \mathbb{MC}^{2D} in exchange of a service from the desired \mathcal{M} . The *multi-redeem protocol* can be executed by \mathcal{C} while the \mathbb{MC}^{2D} is not expired, i.e., while $\tau_{now} \leq \tau_{exp}$.

This protocol defines a four steps exchange, where \mathcal{C} can multi-redeem various coupons from different multicoupons with \mathcal{M} using a single transaction. This fact enhances the computing and networking efficiency, as we will explain in §8.

In order to execute the exchange, \mathcal{C} needs to send \mathcal{M} a set of payment informations from the first unused coupon within each selected multicoupon up to the value of the requested service. This set of payment information is defined formally as $A_{l_j, j, n_j} = [\omega_{i,j}, (l_j, j), n_j]_{j=1}^J$, i.e., the list of payment information associated to all the first unused coupons together with the corresponding coordinates (l_j, j) and the number of the needed coupons n_j from each selected multicoupon j within \mathbb{MC}_ω .

This set of payment information (A_{l_j, j, n_j}) along the merchant identifier ($id_{\mathcal{M}}$) and a redeem identifier (id_r) are signed by \mathcal{C} (using her group private key $sk_{\mathcal{C}}^G$) and sent to \mathcal{M} . Then, \mathcal{M} verifies that the presented coupons are binded to the \mathbb{MC}^{2D} , and \mathcal{C} has a sufficient number of coupons to pay for the requested service: $\lfloor l_j/2 \rfloor + n_j \leq N_j$. Moreover, \mathcal{M} must check that the $\mathbb{MC}_{\mathcal{P}BS}$ and the presented set of coupons are properly signed: the partially blind signature in the former case, and the group signature in latter case. If verifications do not hold, \mathcal{M} rejects the service request and he does not provide the service to \mathcal{C} .

If it passes validations, \mathcal{C} should send signed (using $sk_{\mathcal{C}}^G$) the set of proof information binded to A_{l_j, j, n_j} . This proof information is used by \mathcal{M} to validate the previously sent payment information. The set of proof information is defined formally as $B_{p_j, j} = [\omega_{i+1, j}, (p_j, j)]_{j=1}^J$ where $p_j = l_j + (2n_j - 1)$ depicts the position of the proof information to be used in the multicoupon j . If all verifications hold and all coupons are not previously used, \mathcal{M} updates his database with the received set of coupons. Otherwise, \mathcal{M} will reject \mathcal{C} 's request. The reuse detection and avoidance can be performed checking whether any single coupon is in the \mathcal{M} 's local database or in the \mathcal{I} 's global database executing the claim protocol (see §6.6).

Finally, \mathcal{M} sends \mathcal{C} a signed message as a proof of the accepted coupons.

6.6. Claim Protocol

The *claim protocol* (Figure 6) is executed by \mathcal{M} to request \mathcal{I} a money deposit in exchange of a set of received coupons from customers (as *issue protocol* does, *claim protocol* uses a single transaction to send multiple coupons). This protocol can be executed any time before τ_c ($\tau_{now} \leq \tau_c$), thus \mathcal{M} can execute partial claims, for example, at the end of the day.

When the *claim protocol* is executed, \mathcal{I} performs a list of verifications over the data sent by \mathcal{M} . For example, whether \mathcal{M} is actually affiliated (included in the merchants affiliation list), and some checks similar to those made at the multi-redeem phase. If all

FIGURE 4. Issue protocol flow.

FIGURE 5. Multi-redeem protocol flow.

verifications are successful, \mathcal{I} authorizes a deposit that can be done through a method that is out of scope of this paper (e.g., a deposit made by e-cash or into a bank account). If some verification fails, \mathcal{I} stops the transaction and notifies it to \mathcal{M} . If \mathcal{I} detects an already spent coupon (reuse attempt), he sends a request to \mathcal{G} together with the data sent by \mathcal{M} in order to prove the reuse. \mathcal{G} checks it using the received data and if he also concludes that a reuse has been tried, then he can reveal the identity of the misbehaving customer through the use of the *Open^G* procedure (as explained in §4.1). Then, \mathcal{C} 's identity may be reported to the proper authority in order to proceed as that authority determines.

6.7. Refund Protocol

The *refund protocol* is an optional protocol that can be applied if the involved parties agree. It is used by \mathcal{C} to request \mathcal{I} a reimbursement of unspent coupons when the MC^{2D} is no longer valid and it is not fully used. This protocol can be executed while $\tau_c < \tau_{now} \leq \tau_r$. Note that this time range is later than the time window where \mathcal{M} is allowed to request a deposit in exchange of a list of coupons received from customers. So, it is clear that whether \mathcal{M} has claimed all of his received coupons, no problems arise with double-claims, because whether \mathcal{C} tries to refund coupons already claimed by \mathcal{M} , \mathcal{I} could ask \mathcal{G} to revoke \mathcal{C} 's anonymity. The protocol flow is omitted because it is quite similar to the *claim protocol*. The only remarkable difference is the fact that \mathcal{C} remains anonymous, i.e., she does not send data digitally signed using her digital credentials. If the protocol ends properly, \mathcal{I} authorizes a refund analogous to the *claim protocol* specification. Otherwise, if \mathcal{C} tries to cheat, then \mathcal{I} can request \mathcal{G} to revoke \mathcal{C} 's anonymity in the same way as *claim protocol* defines.

7. DISCUSSION OF SECURITY REQUIREMENTS

In this section we present a formal analysis of our MC^{2D} scheme to verify that it fulfills the desired security requirements under the security model defined in §2.

7.1. Unforgeability

THEOREM 7.1. Under the RSA factorization problem, the one-wayness and collision resistant of a cryptographic hash function and the SDH assumption of the BBS group signature, the multicoupon scheme described in §5 is unforgeable w.r.t. the Definition 2.3.

Proof. We prove that the scheme meets all the considered instances of multicoupon forge provided by the unforgeability games described in §2.3. According to that, to forge a multicoupon it is necessary: to forge the partially blind signature scheme, to find a collision in the cryptographic hash function or to forge the group signature scheme.

In order to simplify the proof notation related to the game 0, let us consider a *prover* to refer to the adversary \mathcal{A}_0 who tries to use a forged coupon (a malicious customer who redeems a forged coupon) and a *verifier* to denote the honest entity who receives a coupon from the *prover* (a merchant who verifies a redeemed coupon or an issuer who checks a coupon received from a merchant).

Besides, let us suppose the *prover* tries to forge a multicoupon using a coupon $(\omega_{i,j})$ beyond the limits of the multicoupon, i.e. a coupon such as its index is either $i > N_j$ or $i \leq 0$. By construction, the multicoupon identifiers $([\omega_{0,j}]_{j=1}^J)$ are blinded and linked to the common data during the *Issue* protocol. The common data contains the number of coupons between a given multicoupon identifier $(\omega_{0,j})$ and the corresponding seed $(\omega_{N_j,j})$, as well as other parameters. \mathcal{I} signs these data using a partially blind signature scheme and as a result, \mathcal{C} obtains locally MC^{2D} . Then, the *verifier* can compare the provided index with the number of coupons bounded in MC^{2D} . It is easy to prove that whether the presented index is $i > N_j$ or $i \leq 0$, the *verifier* does not accept the coupon.

Another forge attempt arises whether the *prover* tries to use a coupon $(\omega_{i,j})$ beyond the limits of the multicoupon, as before, but providing an index within the allowed range ($0 < i \leq N_j$). By hash chain properties, the *verifier* can check whether the provided coupon is included in the multicoupon applying iteratively i times the hash function on it. The *verifier* compares the result with the corresponding multicoupon identifier $(\omega_{0,j})$ and if they are not the same, the *verifier* concludes that the provided coupon does not belong MC^{2D} .

The *prover* could try to use a coupon not belonging MC^{2D} without the *verifier* detecting it. It would mean that the hash function has been broken, due to the fact the *prover* has been found a collision. Since our scheme uses a secure cryptographic one-way hash function with collision resistance, this forge instance, based on finding a collision or a preimage of a hash value, has negligible probability to happen.

Additionally, the *prover* could try to modify some of the parameters bounded in the common data, e.g. increase the number of coupons in a multicoupon, modify their value or extend some of the provided time marks. The modification of the common data implies the modification of MC^{2D} . Thus, when the *verifier* checks the partially blind signature through the use of *Verify^{PBS}*, the *verifier* detects that the MC^{2D} has been modified, since the equation does not hold. So, the *prover* cannot modify the MC^{2D} without it being detected by the *verifier* due to the fact the partially blind signature scheme is unforgeable.

Finally, let us suppose a *prover* trying to use a coupon from a self-issued MC^{2D} . In this case, the *verifier* can detect that MC^{2D} has been issued by an unrecognized \mathcal{I} . Thus, the *verifier* does not accept MC^{2D} .

FIGURE 6. Claim protocol flow.

Regarding the game 1, let us first remember that during the **Issue** protocol, \mathcal{I} knows how many coupons have been issued ($\mathcal{Z}_{\mathcal{I}}$), since one of the parameters included in every public common data is the number of coupons within each multicoupon (and their corresponding value, $[(N_j, v_j)]_{j=1}^J$). \mathcal{A}_1 can try to modify the common data in order to increase the number of coupons available in MC^{2D} . However, since the common data is partially blind signed during the **Issue** protocol, it cannot be modified without being detected using the $\text{Verify}^{\mathcal{PBS}}$ procedure, unless the partially blind signature scheme has been forged. But it is not possible to happen with non-negligible probability due to the fact the used partially blind signature is unforgeable based on the RSA factorization problem (see §3.3 from [17]). Thus, it is not possible with non-negligible probability that an adversary \mathcal{A}_1 can claim more coupons than the number of coupons issued by \mathcal{I} .

Moreover, \mathcal{A}_1 cannot claim more coupons than the number of coupons redeemed by honest customers (\mathcal{Z}_R), since each coupon received from a particular \mathcal{C} is group signed by the use of the group signature scheme. So, \mathcal{A}_1 should either modify the group signature (to fake and increase the number of coupons redeemed by honest customers) or find a collision in the hash function (to find a coupon not rightfully allowed). On one hand, the former forge instance is not possible due to the use of

the BBS group signature, which is unforgeable under the SDH assumption (see §3.1 and Definition 3.1 from [18]). On the other hand, the latter forge attempt is also not possible because of collision resistance property of the cryptographic hash function.

Formally, if an adversary $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{A}_0, \mathcal{A}_1)$ can forge MC^{2D} , as exposed in §2.3, it means that the adversary \mathcal{A} has success trying to forge the partially blind signature, trying to find a collision of a cryptographic hash function or trying to forge the BBS group signature. In order to forge the used \mathcal{PBS} scheme, since it is based on the RSA factorization problem, the adversary have to know the factorization of n . It means that \mathcal{A} needs to break the discrete logarithm problem, which it is assumed to be unfeasible (in \mathcal{K}). As we use a secure one-way collision resistant hash function, it is not possible by an adversary to compute a collision in the hash function with non-negligible probability (in \mathcal{K}). Finally, the forge of the group signature scheme implies to breaking the SDH assumption, which is considered hard if group settings are carefully selected (refer to [14]). Then, it follows that $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{A}_0, \mathcal{A}_1)$ cannot win any forge game with non-negligible probability.

Remark 7.1. \mathcal{C} cannot redeem more coupons than they have been rightfully allowed, issue new multicoupons or modify its content, and \mathcal{M} cannot claim more

coupons than the number of issued coupons by \mathcal{I} or claim more coupons than the number of coupons redeemed by customers.

7.2. Unlinkability

THEOREM 7.2. Under both the Decision Linear problem from the BBS group signature scheme and the unlinkability of the partially blind signature scheme, the multicoupon scheme presented in §5 is 2D-unlinkable w.r.t. the Definition 2.4.

Proof. First, different MC^{2D} have different and unrelated multicoupon identifiers $([\omega_{0,j}]_{j=1}^J)$. Thus, two different coupons from different MC^{2D} ($\mathbf{c}_j(m) \in \text{MC}_\omega$ and $\mathbf{c}'_j(m) \in \text{MC}_{\omega'}, \forall j$) cannot be linked. It is easy to prove, due to the fact that multicoupons are generated applying iteratively the hash chain procedure over different and randomly chosen seed identifiers ($\omega_{N_j,j}$ are uniformly distributed over \mathbb{Z}_r). As a result, their corresponding multicoupon identifiers will be different and unrelated $([\omega_{0,j}]_{j=1}^J \neq [\omega'_{0,j}]_{j=1}^J)$.

Regarding to the unlinkability game 0, we need to take into account that \mathcal{C} signs each set of released coupons during the **Multiredeem** protocol using the BBS group signature scheme, with her group member private key ($sk_{\mathcal{C}}^G$). So, even coupons from different multicoupons are not related due to the above proof, it must be also unfeasible to link two group signed coupons released by the same \mathcal{C} who uses, obviously, the same group member private key. Note that elements output by the $Sign^G$ algorithm are computed based on other elements randomly chosen from \mathbb{Z}_q (the size of \mathbb{Z}_q depends on the size of the security parameter \mathcal{K}), so all of the elements of a signature are uniformly distributed along the input set \mathbb{Z}_q . By the Decision Linear assumption (we refer the reader to §3.2 and Theorem 4.1 from [18]), it can be proven that elements contained in two different group signatures computed by the $Sign^G$ algorithm are indistinguishable. In a formal way, if the adversary \mathcal{A}_0 win the unlinkability game 0, it means that \mathcal{A}_0 can link two group signatures applied on two coupons released by \mathcal{C} . However, it is not possible due to no p.p.t adversary \mathcal{A}_0 can win the game with non-negligible linkability advantage under the Decision Linear problem (in \mathcal{K}).

Concerning the unlinkability game 1, we prove that the multicoupon scheme does not allow the linkability of an **Issue** run with a **Multiredeem** run. It is the same as proving that the $\text{MC}_{\mathcal{P}BS}$ element, used during the **Multiredeem** execution, cannot be linked to the corresponding **Issue** process. Let us consider that \mathcal{A}_1 has access to an issuing view provided by a corrupted issuer ($\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{I}}^{Issue}$). Note that only \mathcal{C} knows the final result of an **Issue** protocol: the $\text{MC}_{\mathcal{P}BS}$ is computed locally by \mathcal{C} , thanks to the last step of the protocol (unblinding). Thus, \mathcal{I} does not know the MC^{2D} identifier $([\omega_{0,j}]_{j=1}^J)$. As a consequence, \mathcal{A}_1

neither knows this identifier, since it is not included within $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{I}}^{Issue}$. Now, consider \mathcal{A}_1 has also executed a **Multiredeem** with a customer \mathcal{C}' (without knowing whether it is the same as \mathcal{C} or not), obtaining a new view $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{A}_1}^{Multiredeem}$. \mathcal{A}_1 can explore data collected in $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{I}}^{Issue}$ and $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{A}_1}^{Multiredeem}$, trying to found a link between $\text{MC}_{\mathcal{P}BS}$ and the corresponding **Issue**. If \mathcal{A}_1 can link $\text{MC}_{\mathcal{P}BS}$ with its **Issue** execution, it means that \mathcal{A}_1 can break the unlinkability of the underlying partially blind signature. However, it only happens with negligible probability (see unlinkability proof §3.4 from [17]), so we have proved that no p.p.t. adversary \mathcal{A}_1 can win the unlinkability game 1 with non-negligible advantage (in \mathcal{K}).

Remark 7.2. Hence, we achieve an \mathcal{MC} -2D-unlinkable scheme, since an adversary $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{A}_0, \mathcal{A}_1)$ cannot link neither two **Multiredeem** instances nor an **Issue** together with a **Multiredeem** run with non-negligible advantage (in \mathcal{K}).

7.3. Anonymity of Customers

THEOREM 7.3. Under the full-anonymity (*CPA-full-anonymity*¹) of the underlying BBS group signature, the multicoupon scheme described in §5 is anonymous w.r.t. the Definition 2.5.

Proof. $\text{MC}_{\mathcal{P}BS}$ convey two types of data: common information (expiration time, number and value of coupons), which can be read by anyone and it does not contain data about its owner; and blind data (multicoupons identifiers $[\omega_{0,j}]_{j=1}^J$). Then, no customer identification data is contained in the $\text{MC}_{\mathcal{P}BS}$.

Firstly, let us consider an adversary \mathcal{A}_0 (operating as a malicious \mathcal{I}) who tries to identify a customer exploring data in $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{A}_0}^{Issue}$. It is trivial to prove that \mathcal{A}_0 cannot obtain any useful data to do that (with non-negligible probability), since \mathcal{C} does not provide any type of information related to her identity during the **Issue** protocol.

Secondly, consider an adversary \mathcal{A}_1 (acting as a malicious \mathcal{M} or a coalition of them) trying to identify a customer processing the $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{A}_1}^{Multiredeem}$ filled during a run of the **Multiredeem** protocol. When \mathcal{C} sends either a single coupon or a set of coupons (either A_{l_j,j,n_j} or $B_{p_j,j}$) to \mathcal{A}_1 , she provides \mathcal{A}_1 these coupons group signed by her group private key ($sk_{\mathcal{C}}^G$). Therefore, \mathcal{A}_1 can only know whether the provided signature is valid and made by a customer who belongs a group of customers using the $Verify^{\mathcal{P}BS}$ algorithm. It is due to the definition and the proof provided by Theorem 5.2 of [18], stating that there is no adversary who can break the group signature anonymity (since it is not possible to break the semantic security of Linear encryption) with non-negligible probability.

¹The BBS short group signature is proven under the CPA-full-anonymity model defined in [18], where an adversary cannot query the opening oracle.

As a result, neither \mathcal{A}_0 nor \mathcal{A}_1 can infer the identity of an honest \mathcal{C} with non-negligible probability. Note that, \mathcal{G} is the only entity who can revoke the anonymity and disclose the identity of \mathcal{C} using the $Open^G$ procedure from the BBS group signature scheme.

7.4. Coupon Reuse Avoidance

THEOREM 7.4. Under both the unforgeability of the BBS group signature scheme the multicoupon scheme presented in §5 allows detecting and avoiding coupon reuse w.r.t. the Definition 2.6.

Proof. \mathcal{I} does not require to store any information about the \mathbb{MC}^{2D} during the Issue protocol, because the \mathbb{MC}^{2D} has been signed with \mathcal{I} 's RSA private key and it also contains all the required information for its verification. However, when \mathcal{M} claims to \mathcal{I} in exchange to a set of redeemed coupons from customers, \mathcal{I} stores data about these already used coupons. Now, when \mathcal{C} redeems some coupons in a particular \mathcal{M} , she sends \mathcal{M} the set of data associated to that coupons, that is, the payment and proof information along the pair of merchant and redeem identifiers (i.e. $[id_{\mathcal{M}}, id_r]$). All this information is group signed by \mathcal{C} (both $\mathbb{SG}_{\mathcal{C}}(A_{l_j, j, n_j}, id_{\mathcal{M}}, id_r)$ and $\mathbb{SG}_{\mathcal{C}}(B_{p_j, j}, id_{\mathcal{M}}, id_r)$), and it is used by \mathcal{M} to obtain each individual coupon and check whether any single coupon has been already redeemed, i.e., if any coupon is either in the \mathcal{M} 's local database or in the \mathcal{I} 's global database (on-line verification).

At this point, we can differentiate two cases. First, taking into account the game 0 (as defined in §2.6), an adversary \mathcal{A}_0 can try to redeem an already spent coupon with an honest merchant \mathcal{M} (with identifier $id_{\mathcal{M}}$). In this case, \mathcal{M} can detect it and prove the misbehavior of \mathcal{A}_0 , because each run of the redeem protocol is uniquely identified by the pair of identifiers $[id_{\mathcal{M}}, id_r]$. Thus, the use of the same coupons information ($A_{l_j, j, n_j} - B_{p_j, j}$) at the same merchant in a different redeem run ($id_r \neq id'_r$), proves that \mathcal{A}_0 is misbehaving, with non-negligible probability. Similarly, if \mathcal{A}_0 tries to reuse the same set of coupons in different merchants, the system detects it because the information (different $id_{\mathcal{M}}$ and the same coupons information) is group signed by the adversary, and thus \mathcal{A}_0 is the dishonest participant.

Secondly, in the game 1 (as defined in §2.6), an adversary \mathcal{A}_1 (with identifier $id_{\mathcal{M}}$) attempts to reuse a set of coupons during a Claim protocol run. Now, \mathcal{A}_1 must provide to \mathcal{I} with the set of coupons along the pair of identifiers $[id'_{\mathcal{M}}, id_r]$ signed by the honest \mathcal{C} . If $id'_{\mathcal{M}} = id_{\mathcal{M}}$ and $id'_r = id_r$, it proves \mathcal{A}_1 misbehavior. Hence, if \mathcal{A}_1 tries to modify id'_r to involve \mathcal{C} in an attempt of coupon reuse, \mathcal{A}_1 must break the unforgeability of the scheme. As proved by Theorem 7.1, \mathcal{A}_1 cannot forge either a multicoupon or a coupon with non-negligible probability (in \mathcal{K}). \mathcal{A}_1 could collude with another malicious \mathcal{M}' , but in this case \mathcal{M}' should prove he

has assigned the identifier $id'_{\mathcal{M}} = id_{\mathcal{M}}$ bound to the presented coupons. Therefore, in any case, through the anonymity revocation mechanism, \mathcal{C} cannot be charged with the coupon reuse (see §7.5).

7.5. Anonymity Revocation of Misbehaving Customers

THEOREM 7.5. Under both the unforgeability and the full-traceability property of the underlying BBS group signature scheme, the multicoupon scheme presented in §5 allows the anonymity revocation and the correct identification of customers trying to redeem either forged coupons or coupons already redeemed, w.r.t. the Definition 2.7.

Proof. Due to the unforgeability (already discussed in §7.1) and the *full-traceability* property of the BBS group signature (according to the Theorem 5.3 and the corresponding proof provided in [18]), our multicoupon scheme ensures that all signatures made on coupons, even those created by an adversary \mathcal{A} composed by the collusion of multiple customers (including probably also a malicious merchant or the group manager), trace to the cheating customer of the coalition. Thus, using the algorithm $Open^G$ provided by the BBS group signature and executed by the group manager, an adversary \mathcal{A} can only avoid to be correctly identified with negligible probability, even they are trying to unfairly blame an honest customer. As a consequence, the multicoupon scheme also provides a non-frameability protection to honest customers.

7.6. Merchant disaffiliation

LEMMA 7.6. Due to the use of an affiliation revocation list (\mathcal{AL}) and the fact that merchants do not share sensitive information with the issuer about both customers and the data required to generate multicoupons, the system presented in §5 allows a secure either voluntary or forced disaffiliation of a merchant from the issuer, without it compromising the security of the system, w.r.t. the Definition 2.8.

Proof. \mathcal{M} only needs to know \mathcal{I} 's public key (e, n) and group's public key (pk^G) in order to work in the system. Therefore, merchants do not have either information about customers or another sensitive information, such as the private key used to issue \mathbb{MC}^{2D} . As stated in the definition, two types of disaffiliation can be defined and proved secure as follows.

On one hand, if \mathcal{M} is no more interested in belonging the affiliation and accepting multicoupons issued by \mathcal{I} , he can request his disaffiliation. The process is as simple as removing the merchant identifier $id_{\mathcal{M}}$, assigned to \mathcal{M} at the affiliation stage, from the affiliation list (\mathcal{AL}), due to the fact merchants do not either have information about customers or share data with other merchants from the affiliation.

On the other hand, considering an adversary \mathcal{A} as a misbehaving merchant, \mathcal{I} can force easily the revocation of the affiliation of the \mathcal{A} . \mathcal{I} can remove $id_{\mathcal{M}}$ from the affiliation list (\mathcal{AL}), and include $id_{\mathcal{M}}$ in a affiliation revocation list (\mathcal{ARL}).

In both cases, when a \mathcal{M} tries to claim a set of coupons, he must be authenticated by \mathcal{I} . Moreover, the data provided by \mathcal{M} contains his $id_{\mathcal{M}}$ signed by \mathcal{C} at the redeem phase. Thus, \mathcal{I} can check the affiliation list (\mathcal{AL}) and if it is applicable, \mathcal{I} denies the claim to \mathcal{M} .

Whether the disaffiliation has been voluntary or forced, if a merchant is still accepting coupons from customers after his disaffiliation, this merchant cannot claim more coupons, since \mathcal{I} will deny the claim request due to the fact \mathcal{M} is no longer affiliated. However, it will be only a loss for \mathcal{M} not for customers. As a result, merchants can leave the system without it being compromised regardless of the disaffiliation was either voluntarily or forced.

7.7. Unsplittling

LEMMA 7.7. Due to the hash chain used in the coupon generation of a same multicoupon, the system presented in §5 discourages customer to split and share coupons, and to receive split coupons from another customer without trust each other, because this procedure could compromise the anonymity of a not dishonest customer, according to the Definition 2.9.

Proof. To prove this lemma, we follow the two games described in Definition 2.9. For the sake of simplicity and without loss of generality, we assume in the following proofs that a MIC^{2D} is composed by a single multicoupon, i.e. j will be always $j = 0$.

During the game 0, an adversary \mathcal{A}_0 obtains a valid MIC^{2D} from \mathcal{I} . Then, \mathcal{A}_0 extracts a set of coupons \mathcal{L}_s from MIC^{2D} (i.e. $\mathcal{L}_s \equiv [\omega_{i,0}]_{i=k}^{k+s}$) and gives this list to an honest customer \mathcal{C}_0 . Before \mathcal{C}_0 can redeem some of the received coupons, \mathcal{A}_0 redeems a single coupon $\omega_{r,0} \in \mathcal{L}_s$. Now, \mathcal{C}_0 tries to redeem some of the received coupons, one of them the coupon $\omega_{r,0}$ recently used by \mathcal{A}_0 . The merchant who receives the coupons checks their validity contacting with the issuer who detects the reuse of $\omega_{r,0}$ (see §2.6). As $\omega_{r,0}$ is group signed by the honest customer \mathcal{C}_0 , it is clear that from the point of view of \mathcal{I} , \mathcal{C}_0 is guilty of coupon reuse (see §7.5) even though \mathcal{A}_0 is who really behaved improperly. As a result, the revocation mechanism of the group signature could declare \mathcal{C}_0 unfairly guilty of reusing a coupon.

During the game 1, an adversary \mathcal{A}_1 receives a set of coupons \mathcal{L}_s from an honest customer \mathcal{C}_1 , who previously obtained a valid MIC^{2D} from \mathcal{I} . \mathcal{A}_1 could try to spend a valid coupon not included in the list of shared coupons, $\omega_{r,0} \notin \mathcal{L}_s$, but included in the multicoupon from which the coupons were extracted, i.e. $\omega_{r,0} \in \text{MIC}^{2D}$. In this context, we can distinguish two cases.

In the first one, \mathcal{A}_1 should obtain a coupon with index $i > k + s$, but this process implies that \mathcal{A}_1 has forged a coupon. However, \mathcal{A}_1 has negligible probability of success, as already discussed in §7.1.

In the second one, \mathcal{A}_1 could try to use a coupon with index $0 \leq i < k$. By hash chain properties, we know $\omega_{k,0}$ is obtained applying iteratively s times the hash function on $\omega_{k+s,0}$. So, as \mathcal{A}_1 knows $\omega_{k,0}$ she can easily generate coupons with index $0 \leq i < k$. Therefore, \mathcal{A}_1 could redeem a valid coupon included in MIC^{2D} but not really shared by \mathcal{C}_1 . Later, \mathcal{C}_1 tries to redeem legitimately this not shared coupon, but already used improperly by \mathcal{A}_1 . The merchant who receives the coupon checks its validity contacting with the issuer, who detects the reuse of that coupon (see §2.6). As this coupon is group signed by \mathcal{C}_1 , as in the game 0, the anonymity revocation procedure will declare \mathcal{C}_1 unfairly guilty of coupon reuse (see §7.5) even though who behaves improperly is \mathcal{A}_1 .

Note that this second case can be avoided if \mathcal{C}_1 shares with another customer a set of coupons where the first shared coupon ($\omega_{k,0}$) is the first unused coupon by \mathcal{C}_1 (i.e. $\omega_{k-1,0}$ is the last used coupon from MIC^{2D} by \mathcal{C}_1).

Hence, if customers want either to split and share some coupons from their MIC^{2D} , or to receive split coupons, they assume the risk to be unfairly accused of fraudulent behavior (through the anonymity revocation of the group signature over a set of reused coupons) if they do not trust each other. As a result, our scheme discourages the multicoupon splitting as *weak unsplittability* does.

8. EFFICIENCY COMPARISON

In this section we compare the efficiency of our proposal with the scheme proposed in [10], because that is the unique previous solution designed for a multi-merchant scenario as explained in §3.

We analytically compare the performance in terms of computational cost measured as the operations complexity performed in each protocol run. For simplicity and without loss of generality, we have obtained the computational cost as the number of long and short exponentiations [17, 19, 14]. The rest of operations have been considered negligible compared to exponentiation operations. A hash function cost (e.g. SHA2) is similar to two modular multiplications. Modular multiplications are negligible respect to exponentiations because an exponentiation with an l -bit exponent is the order of l modular multiplications. Thus, considering that a short exponentiation is about 160 bits [19], the number of modular multiplications required in both Armknecht's scheme [10] and in our proposal, is very low with regard to a modular exponentiation.

Table 3 presents an analytical evaluation of the above parameters considering an scenario where each issued multicoupon contains k coupons. As shown in Table

TABLE 3. Multi-Merchant solutions - An analytical evaluation comparison.

	Operations		
	Issue	Redeem	Claim
[10]	$(2k + 9)E_s + 2E_l$	$(16 + 6k)E_s + (4 + 2k)E_l$	$k(2E_s + 2E_l)$
Our proposal	$4E_s + 2E_l$	$31E_s + E_l$	$2E_s + E_l$

k : number of single coupons in a multicoupon

E_s : short exponentiation E_l : long exponentiation

3 and stated by authors in [10], the complexity of their solution is linear in k . This is because each coupon must be signed individually during the issue protocol. In addition, if a customer wants to redeem more than one coupon, the redeem protocol must be run as many times as coupons are needed because the redeem protocol was designed to work with individual coupons. This fact increases the computational cost of the multicoupon scheme because, as we can see in Table 3, the computational cost of Armknecht's scheme is linear w.r.t. k , meanwhile in our scheme is constant w.r.t. k . Even if the number of coupons is low (e.g. $k = 1$) and it is assumed that a long exponentiation can be approximated to nine short exponentiations [19], our solution improves the efficiency of [10]. For example, let us consider a redeem protocol run where $k = 1$, then the number of short exponentiation operations required by Armknecht's scheme is 76 in front of the 40 required in our proposal. That is, our proposal requires around less than half of the operations of Armknecht's scheme.

9. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have presented *MC-2D*, a scheme for multicoupons suitable for multi-merchant scenarios. We prove that it enhances security and efficiency as regards the previous solution that deals with this scenario. Our solution provides the generic security requirements (unforgeability, reuse avoidance and unsplitability) in addition to new mechanisms for increasing the trust of customers and merchants attracting them to the multicoupon system, as we have proved by formal analysis.

On one hand, customers achieve a high degree of privacy (anonymity, unlinkability and confidentiality), and they are protected against malicious merchants. That is, the reuse of coupons by merchants cannot involve the customer who used those coupons honestly. In fact, this kind of behavior by merchants could result in the revocation of their affiliation to the multicoupon system. This disaffiliation, whether it is forced due to a merchant misbehavior or by his own decision, does not cause security problems since the system does not share any kind of sensitive data with merchants. In fact, our proposal is the first one to achieve this property. On the other hand, merchants are protected from malicious customers trying to reuse or forge coupons because the system provides mechanisms to detect and avoid those

misbehaviors. In case of misbehavior, the system can revoke the anonymity of malicious customers to provide their identities to the proper authorities.

Regarding to the efficiency, we show that our scheme outperforms previous proposal, because it is based on lightweight cryptographic operations and it also allows to redeem and claim one or more coupons during the same protocol run. Moreover, a customer can use different coupons of the same multicoupon at different merchants without requiring any agreement and any shared data among the different merchants. It enhances the flexibility of our proposal together with the fact that the customer and the issuer can agree on the value and the number of coupons of each multicoupon.

FUNDING

This work was partially financed by the European Social Fund and the CONSOLIDER-ARES research project [CSD2007-00004].

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